

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MITIKU****FIRST NAME: AYCHILUHIM****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)
The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I have been involved in essay writing when I was working on my postgraduate thesis and different articles in my professional experience. However, I understood that the research papers were not prepared as per the standard described in the course pack. I have not practiced the Turabian writing style in detail in my previous experiences. Since I am not a native English speaker, the course gave me a detailed insight into basic principles of essay writing such as writing styles, citations, proper use of punctuation in quotations, methods of citation, and quotation. In addition, it is very helpful for me to prepare a series of essays at the Euclid University. This is important in preparing myself to write an evidence-based article in the areas of international public health.

2) THE COURSE PACK

The course pack impressed me to cite references by using in-text or list of works cited by using quotations and paraphrases. I used to not properly paraphrase while citing someone's work. The course gave me an opportunity to clarify this and be able to make a correct paraphrasing and write the author's own words without changing the original meaning (EUCLID 2015, 24). It gives me a clue on how I can cite long quotations thereby avoiding plagiarism. The course pack also indicates how I can construct sentences and paragraphs by using action verbs and limiting series of prepositional clauses to transmit clear information for the audiences. In addition, unlike the previous courses I received in my universities, this course emphasized the importance of inclusion of a comma before the conjunction "and" to reduce ambiguity and increase the effectiveness of the sentences. Furthermore, the course pack has simplified for me to understand when I can use "I" and "me" mainly during compound subjects by easily identify subject pronoun and object pronoun (EUCLID 2015, 47-49).

Usually, universities used their own writing styles like font, manuscript layout, structure, paragraph numbering, indentation, and others. I understand the Euclid University recommended using Chicago Rules (Turabian) or US writing styles in all essay writing like response papers, major papers, and dissertations (EUCLID 2015, 52-54). The US versus UK English difference in spelling, grammar, syntax, and general use gave me an opportunity to identify the difference and to apply in my essay writing (EUCLID 2015, 54-58).

a) Chicago Style and Usage

I have been using abbreviations when I am writing essays and introduced at the beginning of the document. However, I had difficulties to write with quotations, periods and scholarly abbreviations outside the parentheses. In addition, the plural form of the acronyms was not used without apostrophes. The course pack underlined areas where abbreviations should be used like honorifics initials, on envelopes and mailing labels, however, recommended limiting their numbers in a document and avoid using at the beginning of the sentences (EUCLID 2015, 65-66).

Capitalization is one of the major errors for non-native English speaking students and gave me an opportunity to identify the forms and proper use of capitalization like “*full caps, heading caps, and sentence caps.*” Turabian style recommends using capitalization at headlines or headings, the first and last words, and all nouns and the first word of a title or heading, the title of books and articles, compound ethnics and geographic names. I acknowledged how we can hyphenate compound words when we are using it as an adjective or not as nouns. In addition, the manual emphasized the use of italics and quotation marks when we write keywords, titles in the text and references, and foreign names during essay writing (EUCLID 2015, 67-69).

I usually have difficulties when I use numbers during essay writing. The course gave me a clear picture of how to use a spelled-out number during whole numbers, round numbers and beginning of a sentence while numerals for exact quantity. I appreciated the explanation of not written numbers when we referring similar things like “only 10 of hundred mothers delivered at the health facilities.” Ellipsis is also commonly used to omit phrases or words in a sentence. The course pack clearly explained where and when can I used it with a comma, semicolon, question mark, and exclamation points. I clearly understand ellipsis should not be used at the beginning or after the last word of a quotation (EUCLID 2015, 69-71).

b) Chicago Page Formats

Formats and styles are important issues to be considered when we write term papers, thesis, or dissertations. Turabian suggested using a single readable widely available typeface like Times New Roman with twelve-point type at the body of the text. Regarding the spacing, Turabian used double space in text paper while single space when we write block quotations, table title, figure captions, and list of an appendix (Turabian 2013, 221-

222). The course pack also mentioned to justify the right margin and leave one-inch margin across the edge of the pages but may consider more inches at the left edges for binding. I am interested in the application of footnotes when we write an essay. The course pack highlighted it to separate with ruler, begins with a new line, single space but blank line between the notes. I used to put a subscription of numerical when I was writing footnotes. I also appreciated the use of numerical followed by periods and the addition of bibliography to easily find the sources for the readers (EUCLID 2015, 72-73).

Tables are frequently used in term papers, thesis, or dissertations to present a large number of data that is easily understandable by the readers. The course pack highlighted to limit the information, which is not mentioned in the text to clearly understand the contents. In addition, block paragraphs and single spacing to be used while double-spacing between the blocks. The course pack also highlighted to use footnotes and endnotes when the contents are adapted from another source. It also describes the use of footnotes as source lines, general footnotes that apply to the whole, footnotes that apply to specific parts of the table, and notes on levels of statistical significance (EUCLID 2015, 74-75).

3) CONCLUSION

The course gave an opportunity to revise the basic principles and method of essay writing like citation, use of footnote and endnotes, US versus British English differences and effect. It also described the Chicago style and its usage that includes abbreviations, capitalization, numbering, italic and quotation mark, and the Latin abbreviations. In addition, I was impressed with the contents of the course pack, which would be a bridge stone for me to write series of essays in my Department of International Public Health (DIPH) program and prepare state of the art publications related to public health. Furthermore, the Turabian style that I did not use before was briefly explained with practical examples. This was one of my focus areas in this course since the consecutive essays will be prepared based on this guide. However, the course pack has many contents with brief examples, table of contents and page number was not included.

REFERENCES

Euclid University. 2015. ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1. Retrieved from: <http://www.eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>

Kate L. Turabian. 2013. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

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